

Brightspot & Selected Policy Instrument Assessment

Q1-4 only applicable to brightspot assessment.

1. Preliminaries

To be copied from brightspot spreadsheet [will do this before sending this around]

- ID
- DOI
- Title

2. Exclusion/Inclusion

Yes/No; If “No” for any of the three questions below, no further coding needed.

- Are there any policy instruments or support tools associated with this case?
- Is there evidence for diverse value approaches concerning this case?
- Is there evidence for elements of transformative governance?

CODING STAGE II

3. What policy instruments are associated with the case

List specific instruments mentioned in the paper.

4. Category of Policy instrument

- Legal and regulatory instruments e.g. protected areas; land degradation neutrality targets;
- Economic and financial instruments e.g. payment for ecosystem services; ecological fiscal transfers; REDD+;
- Rights-based instruments and customary norms e.g. indigenous community conserved areas (ICCAs);
- Social and cultural instruments e.g. voluntary sustainability standards; eco-labelling certification schemes.

5. Elements of transformative governance present

- Address Status Quo,
- Address Diverse Values,
- Stimulate Institutional Changes,
- Capacity Building,
- Integrative-Adaptive
- Sub-indicators in transformative governance (IPBES VA Chapter 6 - Transformative Governance within Policy Instruments and Initiatives)

6. Decision making contexts

What decision-making contexts are relevant in this case?

- Political decisions & Public actors

- Political decisions & private actors
- Political decisions & civil society actors
- Economic decisions & Public actors
- Economic decision & private actors
- Economic decisions & civil society actors
- Socio-environmental decisions & Public actors
- Socio-environmental decisions & private actors
- Socio-environmental decisions & civil society actors

7. Stakeholders

Which actors and influencers are involved in this case?

- IPLCs (Actors)
- Resource Users (Actors)
- Civil Societies (incl. consumers & different interest groups/gender etc)
- Youth (Actors)
- Media (Influencers)
- Intergovernmental Organizations (Influencers & Actors)
- National/Subnational Governments (Influencers & Actors)
- Private sector (Influencers & Actors)
- Donors (Influencers)
- NGOs/SCOs (Influencers & Actors)

8. Which broad values, specific values and life frames are accounted for in the application of this policy instrument:

- Broad Values: Principles (respect, care, kinship)
- Specific Values: Instrumental, Relational, Intrinsic
- Life Frames (ways in which nature matters to people): Living from, living with, living in, living as

9. Scales

- At what scale is this policy instrument implemented in this case: local, landscape, provincial/state, national, regional, international, cross-scale

10. In which way did the application of policy support tools facilitate incorporation of (a) diverse value approaches and transformative governance

The kind of dimensions will differ from case to case, but elements that will be useful to mention here will include: what is the evidence for transformative governance presented (refer to sub-indicators), in which way were policy support tools used to facilitate policy implementations, how were stakeholders involved, were multiple policy approaches used?

Lower Priority Questions for this round

11. Which critical capacities were required for uptake and/or transformation?
12. Any mentioned gaps, unintended consequences/feedbacks?
13. Specific Options for policy makers mentioned?